

First records of the white widow spider *Latrodectus pallidus* O.P.-Cambridge, 1872 from South Africa (Araneae: Theridiidae)

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ABSTRACT: The white widow spider *Latrodectus pallidus* O.P.-Cambridge, 1872 was described from Israel. The species has a wide distribution and is now commonly found throughout North Africa, the Middle East, and Central Asia. During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), *L. pallidus* was for the first time recorded from South Africa. The known distribution from South Africa is provided, with notes on the morphology and behaviour.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, new record, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Latrodectus* Walckenaer, 1805 is represented by 34 species with a wide distribution (World Spider Catalog, 2022). The genus was revised in the Afrotropical Region by Lotz (1994) and the six species recorded from South Africa were well documented in the First Spider Atlas of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010) as well as the Identification Guides (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). The number of species from the country was recently increased to seven, with the description of a new species, *L. umbukwane* Wright *et al.*, 2019, from KwaZulu-Natal (Wright *et al.* 2019).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), more than 5 400 theridiid specimens were sampled, of which 10% were *Latrodectus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015, 2012). Among this material and photographs received, several specimens were identified as *L. pallidus* O.P.-Cambridge, 1872, representing the first records from South Africa. Additional information on their morphology, distribution in South Africa, and behaviour are provided here.

TAXONOMY

Latrodectus pallidus was originally described from Israel (World Spider Catalog, 2022) and is also found in North Africa, the Middle East, and Central Asia. The common name for the species in English is the white widow spider. The main distinguishing characteristics are the creamy white abdomen bearing dorsally six small black spots arranged in pairs present in males and females (Figs 1, 2, 7).

Figures 1–6. *Latrodectus pallidus* line drawings: 1. Line drawing male abdominal pattern. 2. Female abdominal pattern. 3. Female abdominal setae. 4. Female epigyne. 5. Female internal genitalia. 6. Male palp. (After Lotz, 1994).

In a juvenile sampled from Dwarskersbos, the black spots were absent (Fig. 10). The female is also recognised by the short sparse abdominal setae (Fig. 3). Venter of abdomen is black with a yellowish-white hourglass marking between the epigastric furrow and spinnerets (Figs 8–9). The carapace is brown with darker tint around the margins (Fig. 11). The legs are faintly banded.

The male palp has an embolus with three loops (Fig. 6). The female epigynal atrium is about twice as wide as long (Fig. 4) and spermathecal ducts have three loops (Fig. 5) (Levi, 1966, Lotz, 1994).

Figures 7–8. *Latrodectus pallidus*: 7. Female from Kloovenberg dorsal view. 8. Female from Kasteelberg ventral view. Photo credits: Cecile Roux.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Cape Verde, Israel, Iran, Libya, Asian Russia, Turkey, Yemen. New record: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Gauteng: Irene field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23). **Western Cape:** Koringberg, Mooresburg (-33.15, 18.65); Kasteelberg, Riebeeck West (-33.47, 18.52); Kloovenburg Riebeeck Kasteel (-33.47, 19.04); Dwarskersbos (-32.42, 18 14).

LIFESTYLE

They construct a web at a height of 30–60 cm between the twigs of shrubs or soil debris in a variety of microhabitats. The spiders make use of the same web over a long period of time and the small male is found on the border of the web of the female. Information on the biology of *L. pallidus* is provided by Shulov (1940).

The juvenile photographed at Dwarskersbos made a circular retreat, incorporating small stones in the webbing (Fig. 10). The specimen collected at Irene was found under a dry leaf on the soil surface (Fig. 12).

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Figures 9–12. *Latrodectus pallidus*: 9. Juvenile from Dwarskersbos, ventral view. 10. Juvenile in retreat from Dwarskersbos. 11. Female from Kasteelberg. 12. Female dorsal view from Irene. Photo credits: 9–11. Cecile Roux. 12. Peter Webb.

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